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Oncogenic KRas activates CDYL2.

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We describe here the function of oncogenic mutant KRas G12V in transcriptional activation of CDYL2. Interestingly, wild-type KRas instead silenced CDYL2. The data demonstrate a biologically relevant relationship between oncogene activation and mobilization of the endogenous imprinting system in transformation in humans.